

ISic3281

I.Sicily inscription 3281

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἐνθάδε κείμε

1. Βάσσοις ἰατρός

3. ἔζησεν ἔτη

4. ν

5. ἐτελεύτησεν

6. τῆ πρὸς ἰε κα(λανδῶν) Μαρ(τίων)

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (eng)

Here lies Bassos the doctor. He lived for 50 years, and died 15 days before the kalends of March.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645549

PHI 316253

Bibliography

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